

Why is Quantum Mechanics Sometimes Formulated Using Fisher Information? Part II

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In (1), a variational approach is applied to Fisher's information (with constraints) to obtain a differential equation in $P(x)$ =probability to be at x . It is suggested the equation may be simplified using $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is real. The result is the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation with $m=1$. As a first observation, we note that Fisher's information, which is a purely statistical quantity, should not necessarily yield a nonrelativistic equation which is an approximation of relativistic results. In particular, we argue that Fisher's information is used to find $\langle p^2 \rangle$ not necessarily $1/2m \langle p \rangle$, but this is a minor point.

A more important issue, we argue, is the meaning of $P(x)$ in a bound system. A classical bound system is sometimes said to have a $P(x)=C/v(x)$ i.e. $P(x)dx$ is proportional to dt , the amount of time a particle spends in each equally sized dx . In the high energy limit, the envelope of a quantum bound probability $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction) is said to roughly match $C/v(x)$, yet this density does not follow from the extremization of Fisher's information (together with two general constraints which yield E and $V(x)$ =potential). This begs the question: What is $P(x)$?

If one considers a particle moving at constant speed (i.e constant momentum) then $P(x)$ =constant because each dx point carries the same probability. Classically a particle placed in a box with infinite potential walls would have a $P(x)$ =constant and p and $-p$ motion would be separated in time. Thus if $P(x)$ is to have meaning in a box, one must conclude that the probabilities associated with p and $-p$ are not constant, but rather functions of x . This then leads to the notion of a complex new kind of probability (which maps to $P(x)$ =constant) for a free particle i.e. $W(x) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ so that the modulus $W^*(x)W(x)=P(x)=1$. These ideas seem to go beyond the notion of Fisher information.

What then is the role of Fisher information? We argue it is related to two very specific moments of the distribution $\cos(px)$ or rather $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\cos(px)$ with $a(p)=a(-p)$, namely $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle p^2 \rangle$. In classical physics there exists p and p^2 at each x point (but one is the square of the other), but with distributions $\langle p \rangle$ does not equal to $\langle p^2 \rangle$ in general. Both $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle p^2 \rangle$ are linked to physical concepts which exist in Newtonian mechanics, namely impulse and work. With the presence of $\cos(px)$ one has a combination of Newtonian mechanics and a statistical distribution. We argue that the role of Fisher's information is to allow one to transform from $\langle p \rangle$ to $\langle p^2 \rangle$. In particular, $-idW/dx$ appears in Fisher's information (and is linked to $\langle p \rangle$), but the specific role of a variation is to transform it into $\langle p^2 \rangle$ which appears in a conservation of energy equation. We argue that this is why Fisher's information may be used to derive the Schrodinger equation.

The Meaning of $P(x)$ = probability to be at x

In (1), the Schrodinger equation is derived by varying Fisher's information with respect to some basic constraints (which ultimately lead to $E W(x)$ and $V(x)W(x)$). Fisher's information is given by:

$$I = \int dx P(x) \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P(x)) \right\} \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P(x)) \right\} \quad ((1))$$

We ask: Why should there be a $P(x)$ in the first place? In a classical bound system with equal dx spacings in one dimension, it is sometimes said that there exists a $P(x)$ proportional to $dt(x)$. $P(x)$ is then $C/v(x)$, but this density does not follow from the extremization of Fisher's information. This is interesting because the envelope of the quantum bound density $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction) is said to match $C/v(x)$. Thus the meaning of $P(x)$ must be different, it seems.

We consider a particle moving in one direction with constant p . In such a case $P(x)=\text{constant}$ as all x points have the same probability or weight. In a classical bound system with p and $-p$ at different times, $P(x)=\text{constant}$, which means one would not use Fisher's information which relies on $P(x)$. What is happening then? It seems there must be an x -probability distribution associated with both $P(x,p)$ and $P(x,-p)$. Separately, $P(x,p)$ and $P(x,-p)$ are constants (because each x point has the same weight), so there should be a new associated probability $W(x)$ which maps into $P(x)=\text{constant}$. This suggests that there is more to $P(x,p)$. In particular it is linked to $\cos(px)+i \sin(px)$ such that the modulus yields $P(x)=\text{constant}$. Thus $P(x)$ is not really the defining quantity, but rather the "square root" type flux or probability. This depends on x and may be linked to Fisher's information. In particular:

$$W(px) + W(-px) = 2 \cos(px) \quad ((2))$$

((2)), however, is not $P(x)$, it is like the square root of $P(x)$. ((2)) may be generalized to:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \cos(px) \quad \text{where } a(p)=a(-p) \quad ((3))$$

for a system in a potential which stirs up all p values. Then $W(x)W(x) = P(x)$ and this may be used in Fisher's information which requires a classical type probability. $P(x)$ is positive and integrates to 1, while $W(x)$ does not.

We note, however, as we did in Part I, that $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-d/dx$ the translation generator and we argue that this is a central idea linked to the free particle probability. It may be deduced from the variation of Fisher's information, but is a somewhat roundabout fashion. This begs the question: What is the purpose of Fisher's information?

Fisher's Information

In the above section, we argued that a free particle which as $P(x)=\text{constant}$ is linked to a spatially dependent square root type flux/probability $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ which is an eigenfunction of the translation generator $-id/dx$. As a result, in the general case of $W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \cos(px)$ (for $a(p)=a(-p)$), one has a probability distribution in p at each x . As a result, one may calculate the first two moments:

$$\text{Sum over } p \ P(x/p) \ p = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p \cos(px) \} / W(x) = -idW/dx / W \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \quad P(x/p) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \quad p^2/2m \cos(px) \} / W(x) = -1/2m \, d/dx \, dW/dx / W \quad ((4b))$$

It may be noted that there is physical meaning attached to p and $p^2/2m$ in classical Newtonian physics. P is linked to impulse (i.e. a particle striking a surface) and $p^2/2m$ to work i.e. force parallel to a distance. Thus the two statistical moments are linked to physical reality, but there now exists spatial probability distributions. Classically p multiplied by itself yields p^2 , but $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle$ does not, in general, yield $\langle p^2 \rangle$. One needs a method to transform from one to the other. We argue that this is the role of Fisher's information.

In particular, Fisher's information is of the form:

$$P(x) \{ d/dx \ln(P(x)) \} \{ d/dx \ln(P(x)) \} = dW/dx \, dW/dx \quad ((5))$$

As a result, for the bound case, it may be rewritten more simply in terms of $W(x)$ which describes the physical x dependency. Varying ((5)) yields:

$$-2 \, d/dx \{ dW/dx \} \quad (\text{using the usual notion of integration by parts}) \quad ((6))$$

Thus one has $d/dx \, dW/dx$ which is proportional to $\langle p^2 \rangle$. One starts with an expression linked to $\langle p \rangle$ and obtains $\langle p^2 \rangle$ which may be used in a conservation of energy equation following the ideas of Newton.

The fact that Fisher's information uses $dW/dx/W$ which follows from $d \ln(P(x))/dx$, suggests that this is an important quantity i.e. translational information is key. In particular, it is the eigenfunction of $-i d/dx$, $\exp(ipx)$, which defines the new probability (associated with $P(x)=1$) for a free quantum particle.

Relativistic Versus Nonrelativistic

In (1), Fisher's information is varied to obtain the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation. Fisher's information, however, is a purely statistical quantity, so why does it give a nonrelativistic rather relativistic result? The nonrelativistic result (Schrodinger equation) is a limiting case of the relativistic Klein-Gordon equation.

We note that in the derivation of (1), $m=1$. If m were not 1, one would have to weight the Fisher information by a constant. Thus, we argue that Fisher's information is really used to create $\langle p^2 \rangle$ from $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle p^2 \rangle$ appears in the relativistic Klein-Gordon equation. Thus, the notion of Fisher's information is just as applicable to relativistic results as to nonrelativistic, although the details are different. We also note that in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases, a free particle is described by $\exp(ipx)$ which is an eigenfunction of $-i d/dx$ (although the definition of p differs for each case).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a free particle is described by a square root type probability $\exp(ipx)$ whose modulus is a constant = $P(x)$. The square root probability is an eigenfunction of

$-i\hbar d/dx$ the translational generator. Fisher's information is a purely statistical integral based on $dP(x)/dx$. Thus one would not use Fisher's information, in general, for a free particle (constant p) moving in one direction or even a classical sum of p and $-p$ because $P(x)=\text{constant}$, Thus we argue that some very different statistical physics occurs in quantum mechanics which maps to the usual classical $P(x)$ which occurs in Fisher's information. One must thus determine the unusual statistical behaviour appearing in quantum mechanics and this may be done without Fisher's information. In particular, one may suggest a square root type flux/probability = $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. It is a dynamic probability, but its modulus is 1 showing that all x points have the same probability. One may note that $P(x)=\text{constant}$ does not depend on p . The price to pay, however, is the notion of a wavelength in $\cos(px)$ which does depend on p i.e. \hbar/p .

One may then create a real function using $W(p,x) + W(-p,x)$ for a bound system. This may be generalized to $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \cos(px)$ for $a(p)=a(-p)$ with $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$. At this point, Fisher's information may be utilized. We first note that it may be written as $I = \text{Integral } dx \frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$.

As a result, the variation of Fisher's information transforms from a quantity based on dW/dx linked to $\langle p \rangle = -i\hbar dW/dx / W$ to $d/dx dW/dx$ linked to $\langle p^2 \rangle = -\hbar^2 d^2W/dx^2 / W$. In classical physics, momentum p squared yields p^2 , but in general, $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle$ is not $\langle p^2 \rangle$ and the latter is required in Newton's conservation of energy equation. Thus the variation of Fisher's information allows one to transform from $\langle p \rangle$ to $\langle p^2 \rangle$ which is required if one has a probability distribution linked to p . That fact that dW/dx , however, is linked to $\langle p \rangle$ and $d/dx dW/dx$ to $\langle p^2 \rangle$ points to $\exp(ipx)$, so Fisher's information does seem to incorporate the idea of $\exp(ipx)$ being an eigenfunction of the translation operator.

References

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